

Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe

Practical Experiences with Intel Xeon Phi

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Abstract

This whitepaper presents experiences integrating Xeon Phi to a cluster system as well as porting and optimizing applications to the Xeon Phi. The focus is on disseminating information and best practices learned from hands-on experience which is not readily available from the standard manuals and other product literature.

Introduction

The Intel Xeon Phi is a novel processor technology introduced in 2012. Its architecture is distinctively different from existing GPGPU and other accelerator architectures. This PRACE white paper presents best practices based on practical experiences with working on a cluster of Xeon Phi.

This white paper is intended to complement the PRACE Xeon Phi Users Guide^{*} and Intel's MPSS User Guide[†] by providing a high-level overview of some of the most common administrative best practices and caveats when deploying the Phi in a cluster environment.

Systems Administration

What makes the Xeon Phi fundamentally different from existing accelerators from a system administration standpoint is the fact that each coprocessor runs a fully-fledged operating system and has a number of associated tools.

This, combined with the open source nature of the whole stack makes it possible to customize the system according to ones needs and makes it possible to simply port existing tools to the Phi. However, in order to use the Phi to its fullest extent some administrative attention is required along with some caveats.

Software Stack

The Intel Manycore Platform Software Stack (MPSS) is a centralized package containing all the software required to run the Xeon Phi. MPSS has undergone many changes since its initial release. These include syntax of commands, configuration files, and file locations.

^{*} <http://www.prace-ri.eu/IMG/pdf/Best-Practice-Guide-Intel-Xeon-Phi.pdf>

[†] <https://software.intel.com/en-us/articles/intel-manycore-platform-software-stack-mpss>

The software stack underwent a very significant change at version 3.1 (Sep 2013) when the underlying OS was changed from a custom Linux build to the YOCTO Linux distribution. This enabled end users to compile the whole Xeon Phi operating system from the source code (making it GPL compliant) and be able to maintain up-to-date security patches.

Changing the Phi's operating system to YOCTO Linux also introduced many changes in the functionality of the MPSS tools and configuration on the host side. At the time of the writing most documentation available on-line still pertains to pre-3.1 versions. It is therefore important that when reading documentation the publication date is checked to ensure one is not trusting outdated information. Typically a trusted source of documentation is the Intel MPSS download page.

In the subsequent releases (3.2, 3.3) in the first half of 2014, further improvements have been introduced in addition to bug fixes. These include:

- Native support for LDAP user authentication
- Support for new OS versions (for notably RHEL7)
- Wider support for InfiniBand fabric drivers

OS Version Dependencies

The software stack is certified to operate with a specified set of operating systems (OS) and drivers. The certification process usually is such that there is a slight gap (2-6 months) when a new OS version is released to when the official support for it arrives. Typically, this happens with the next major or minor release of the software stack. In case of urgent kernel updates, for example due to security exploits, it is possible to recompile the driver for a newer kernel but there is a slight risk that unexpected bugs may arise.

At the time of writing, MPSS (3.3) supports the following operating systems:

- RHEL 6.2+
- RHEL 7.0
- SLES 11
- Windows 7SP1/8 Enterprise
- Windows Server 2012/2013

Infiniband Version Dependencies

On clusters with InfiniBand interconnects, the Phi can be connected directly to the IB fabric via a special SCIF virtual InfiniBand interface. This enables much faster communication between tasks and the ability to use RDMA (Remote Direct Memory Access).

The OpenFabrics (OFED) software stack provides a common layer between the upper-level interfaces such as MPI and the low-level drivers for fabrics using RDMA. The OFED stack is used in practically all clusters which utilize InfiniBand. Intel provides Phi-specific drivers and extensions to the OFED stack in the MPSS package.

During its evolution, the OFED stack has diverged into the standard OFA (Open Fabrics Alliance) OFED and vendor-enhanced stacks from Mellanox and Intel (formerly QLogic). Furthermore, there are two major versions used widely today, 1.5 and 2.0, which are not compatible. The former is typically the standard version shipped with many OS suppliers.

The Xeon Phi supports a specified subset of these OFED stacks and drivers. Thus, it is important when planning the system to choose an OFED stack driver version that is compatible with the Phi.

Installing the OFED stack also introduces a number of services. Care should be taken to start and stop them in the correct order as specified in the MPSS documentation.

Typical Customizations

The basic, default installation of the Xeon Phi works out-of-the-box for using the offload programming model in a single workstation environment. In order to improve the usability and use

Phi's in a multi-node cluster environment, some customization should be performed. Below is a summarization of some of the most common customizations. Unless otherwise stated, these customizations are described in detail in the MPSS Users Guide.

Setting Up Virtual Ethernet Network Bridging

Unless the network bridging is enabled, the card can only be accessed from the local host to which the cards are attached. In order to make the card visible to the cluster, network bridging should be enabled.

One should note that the Ethernet bridge has a relatively low bandwidth and high latency and should not be used for any performance-critical network communication.

Setting Up Virtual InfiniBand Bridging

It is possible to set up IP over InfiniBand (IPoIB) on the Phi InfiniBand interface but at the time of the writing it is available as a technology preview (MPSS 3.3).

Mounting External File Systems

By default, no file systems are mounted on the Intel Xeon Phi and files must be transferred by scp between the host and card. This adds extra workflow steps to stage files in and out of the Xeon Phi and consumes Phi's limited and high-value on-board memory.

It is therefore recommended to mount an external file system to the card. This can either be:

- Via a "virtio" virtual block device on the host
- Mounting of a remote file system via NFS

Mounting of a parallel file system (Lustre, Panasas)

- Some directories which may be sensible to mount from an external source:
- User home and scratch directories
- Application directories containing Phi binaries and libraries (for example /opt)
- /var (each mount pointing to a unique directory on the NFS, for example /share/vars/[hostname of mic])

One may want to initialize a different set of environment variables when users log into the MIC, for example, having the PATH variable pointing to directories with Phi binaries instead of their x86-64 counterparts. However, when mounting the \$HOME directory, the same shell initialization files get loaded. To work around this, one can set a conditional for the host architecture in the shell initialization, for example:

```
if [ `uname -m` == 'k1om' ]; then
    export PATH=$HOME/bin-k1om:$PATH
fi
```

When mounting a parallel file system, one should ensure that the client version on the Phi card is compatible with the server version. At least with Lustre a fairly recent version (2.5) is needed. Further information on Lustre on Phi is available in:

<https://wiki.hpdd.intel.com/display/~dmiter/Lustre+on+Intel+Xeon+Phi>

Integration with the Local User Management

By default, the user accounts on the Xeon Phi are generated using the **micctrl** command based on the host's local user accounts. Oftentimes in a cluster environment the accounts are provided by a network directory service such as NIS or LDAP. In the latest versions of MPSS (3.2 onwards) these are supported.

Execution Auto-offloading

Execution Auto-offloading enables the host OS to automatically detect attempted execution of any Xeon Phi (K1OM) binary on the host and transparently executes it on a Xeon Phi. This technique was developed at CSC during the early evaluation of the Phi and has since been adopted by a number of Phi sites.

While it makes it easier for users to execute native Phi files, the most substantial benefit is simplifying cross-compilation of programs to the Xeon Phi.

Typically the automake-based configuration systems on many software-projects have not been designed to support cross-compiling and fail, usually due to the individual test programs that auto-configure has compiled for the Phi architecture and is trying to run on the host.

This causes the developer to revert to the following workflow:

1. Run `./configure` with the CPU host as the target
2. Edit a large number of Makefiles manually to add the Xeon Phi compilation flags
3. Run `make`

Step 2 especially can be extremely time-consuming and needs to be repeated multiple times.

With the Execution Auto-offloading, the second step can be omitted.

1. Run `./configure` with the Xeon Phi as the target (i.e. `CFLAGS=-mmic`). Test programs compiled within the configure script will transparently be executed on the Phi.
2. Run `make`

Execution auto-offloading is based on the **binfmt_misc** device driver in the Linux kernel. To enable it, two steps must be taken:

1. Configure the `binfmt_misc` driver by feeding a configuration string to `/proc/sys/fs/binfmt_misc/register`. The string contains information on the binary fingerprint to identify a Xeon Phi binary and a pointer to the handler script to process files with the given binary fingerprint.
2. Install a handler script on the host that executes a binary that is passed to it on the Xeon Phi.

The configuration string and the handler script are provided in Appendix 1.

Detailed information on **binfmt_misc** can be found in `binfmt_misc.txt` in the Linux kernel's Documentation directory.

Enabling power management

In order to conserve energy while the Phi is idle, power saving should be enabled. The Phi supports a number of power states: Key states are the C0 active state with frequency scaling; PC6 low power state; and the P01 Turbo state (on the card models where this is available).

There are additional intermediate states with more power consumption than in the idle state but a faster “wake up” time. However, it is to be expected that for typical HPC workloads the aforementioned states are clearly the most important: The active periods for the CPU in HPC are typically long compared to the ~0.5 seconds that it takes to wake up from the deep sleep state. Thus, there is little benefit in using the intermediate states.

The power states can be enabled directly with the **micsmc** command and made persistent with editing the `PowerManagement` line in the `/etc/mpss/micN.conf` file(s).

When measuring power consumption, it is important to note that (at least at the time of writing) the **micsmc** command does not provide reliable power draw results when the card is idle and has power management enabled: the command wakes up the processor from the sleep state. Thus, any idle power draw measurements should be obtained from an external sensor on the host or an intelligent PDU.

Debuggers

When porting applications to the Phi, new bugs may arise. There are several typical reasons for this:

- A constrained amount of memory magnifies the severity of previously harmless minor memory leaks.
- If moving from another compiler to using Intel compiler some underlying compiler functionality may differ (Handling of uninitialized variables, for example).
- The extremely large amount of threads may conflict in ways that was very rare with smaller thread counts.

The debuggers bundled in the Intel Xeon Phi distribution (IDB and GDB) have fairly limited capabilities and are not very user-friendly. The most recent versions of both TotalView and Allinea DDT have support for the Phi and are much more usable.

Conclusions and recommendations

The stand-alone OS of the Xeon Phi allows for numerous customizations but also requires more administration resources to maintain than accelerators. It is recommended that a sufficient lead-time and capable system administration resources are allocated for customizing the software stack before putting the Phi into a production environment. The Phi user community and forums are a valuable source of information as well.

An important consideration is that the Manycore Platform Software Stack (MPSS) has undergone many changes since its inception and there are documents and posts which may be outdated. Thus, one should take special care not to follow outdated documentation.

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